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Monitoring tensile loads in mooring lines using quasi-distributed FBG sensors

^{a*}Michael Lee, ^aJoseph Chung, ^bRichard Akers, and ^cAndrea Copping, PhD

^aCyTroniQ, Los Angeles, CA

^bMaine Marine Composites, LLC, Portland, ME

^cPacific Northwest National Laboratory, Seattle, WA

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Wave energy converters and floating tidal turbines are moving towards commercial deployments, but there is little history of mooring line survival when exposed to high energy environments and to environments conducive to biofouling, or from collisions with vessels or large marine animals. Current information on mooring line integrity comes from periodic maintenance checks and from system failures. By including distributed sensor technology directly into mooring lines, the mechanical performance of the lines can be monitored from shore, allowing for timely dispatch of maintenance crews, decreasing failures, and extending the time between maintenance visits. CyTroniQ has developed a fiber-based sensor system that can be embedded in mooring lines in order to measure changes in the stress and strain of the mooring lines. A comprehensive test program is proposed to validate the performance of the embedded, quasi-distributed sensor system.

Keywords: floating marine energy; mooring lines; sensors for mooring line integrity; Fiber Bragg Grating; technology economic analysis (TEA); cycle life analysis (CLA); operation and maintenance (O&M); environmental monitoring

1. Introduction

According to a recent industry survey from the National Hydropower Association [1] one of the highest priority concerns in the marine energy industry is mooring lines. In storm conditions the instantaneous loads in mooring lines can exceed the weight of the entire system so lines must be strong enough to survive extreme loads without damage. The cost of repairing or replacing a mooring line can be a substantial percentage of the deployment cost, so mooring failures must be minimized. Mooring lines can be weakened by extreme events, accumulated fatigue damage, exposure to UV light, damage from marine organisms, and from marine mammal or ship strikes. Presently operators use tension cells to monitor the loads at line ends, but they could get higher reliability and reduced downtime with a method of monitoring the entire line condition in real time.

This work seeks to determine whether the mooring line material with the embedded technology, can withstand exposure to the marine environment, through tensile tests before and after prolonged exposure to running seawater.

2. The Case for Quasi-Distributed Sensors

The stability and robust operation of anchored marine energy devices are dependent on the integrity of the mooring lines and the attachment to the seafloor. Mooring lines can be damaged in many ways (Table 1), so ensuring that the mooring lines remain intact, as well as receiving early warning of any deterioration in their condition, can prevent failures. Line failures can result in interruptions in service and loss of equipment, and the cost of repairing or replacing a mooring line can be a substantial percentage of the deployment cost.

Early identification of sections of lines with excessive fatigue allows the operator to concentrate on repairing a section rather than an entire line. Scheduled maintenance can be replaced with performance-driven predictive maintenance, reducing mooring system Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs.

The ability to measure loads at discrete locations would allow an operator to detect entanglement with fishing gear and localized damage from collisions immediately. By comparing signals from comparable wave impacts, such a system could detect when excessive marine fouling might affect the lines. Implementing a quasi-distributed sensor system would reduce system risk, which would be a significant benefit for owners, insurance underwriters, and effects on the marine environment from lost gear.

Large mooring lines consist of many sub-ropes, tightly bound into large diameter ropes so that individual fibers are mostly parallel, oriented in the direction of tension. If a sub-rope is cut, tension is passed to other sub-ropes, increasing localized tension, and decreasing the total strength of the line. Tension cells can be used to monitor the loads at rope ends, but degradation and rope damage are often localized events. Distributed sensors can monitor the entire rope condition in real time to determine local degradation as well as loss of strength of the whole line.

3. An Optical Quasi-Distributed Sensor System

CyTroniQ has developed an integrated, quasi-distributed sensor system that can be embedded into synthetic mooring lines to monitor the dynamic strain and static creep along these lines. The CyTro-X system consists of optical fibers with multiple, distributed Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) patches that are sensitive to strain in the fiber. An electro-optical unit (Interrogator) separates signals from each patch and reports the corresponding strains (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Fiber Bragg Gratings: Distributed, Embedded Sensors (Image from Fang, L., Chen, T., Li, R. Application of Embedded Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) Sensors in Monitoring Health to 3D Printing Structures. IEEE SENSORS JOURNAL, VOL. 16, NO. 17, Sept. 1, 2016.)

Figure 2. Previous tensile tests on HMPE rope with embedded CyTro-X distributed sensors. Sensors report line tension, highest in mid-sections, lower in splices.

Previously, CytroniQ tested sections of 54 mm (2-1/8 inch) High Modulus PolyEthylene (HMPE) rope with embedded FBG-equipped optical fibers (Figure 2). Tension was stepped up to 100 tonnes, 55% of the mean breaking strength. The Interrogator demultiplexed the combined FBG signals at multiple locations and reported strains commensurate

Table 1. Potential causes of synthetic mooring line failures.

• Abrasion at shackles	• Ship strikes
• Propeller cuts	• Shark bites
• Collisions with mooring lines, esp. redundant lines	• Impacts from marine mammals (risk to animal)
• Loads from fishing gear entanglement	• Biofouling may damage fibers, increase drag/weight
• Uneven loads at splices	• Indirect damage induced by anchors or piles
• Snap loads associated with extreme events	• Damage from rockslides, earthquakes

with variable rope thicknesses at those locations [2]. Good correlation was observed between the FBG/Interrogator output and applied tension.

Figure 3. FBG Fiber Embedded in Rope

Continuous production methods allow FBG fiber to be built into mooring lines economically and efficiently (Figure 3). Temporal and spatial signatures of loads measured at discrete locations can be used to detect and identify events such as entanglement with fishing gear, localized damage from collisions, and uneven stress due to fatigue damage. By comparing signals from comparable wave impacts, such a system could identify a collision such as a localized shock from a trawler line or a larger, more distributed impact from a whale.

4. Comprehensive Test Plan

A test program will determine whether the synthetic rope material with the embedded CyTro-X sensor fiber can withstand exposure to the marine environment, through tensile tests before and after a three-to-five-month exposure to running seawater. These laboratory tests on sensor-equipped mooring lines will provide proof of concept before continuing to an open water test.

4.1. Rope Test Samples

Table 2. Mooring lines to be tested by CyTroniQ

Qty	Description
2	Polyester, 12-strand ropes, 1-inch diameter
2	Polyester, double braid ropes, 1-inch diameter
2	Aramid, 12-strand ropes, 1-inch diameter
2	HMPE (high modulus polyethylene), 12-strand ropes, 1-inch diameter

Eight sections of synthetic rope (Table 2) will be fabricated from a set of materials chosen as the best candidates for embedding the CyTro-X sensor fiber technology for use in floating marine energy systems. All rope samples will be 8m long including eyes and thimbles and will have one or more CyTro-X fibers installed in strand(s) of the rope. The ropes will be equipped with eyes to attach to MTS tensile test machines. Testing of the mooring line material will follow guidance by the American Bureau of Shipping (ABS)¹, DNV², LR and/or BV as appropriate.

4.2. Procedure, Data Collection, and Analysis

Tensile tests will be performed on rope samples before and after a prolonged seawater soak. The samples will be separated into two sets, Group A that will be exposed to seawater and Group B that will not be exposed to seawater. All of the ropes from Group A and B will be wetted with fresh water and subjected to tensile tests. Stress/strain data will be collected from both an MTS 311.41 tensile test machine (Figure 4) and from a CyTro-X opto-electrical Interrogator. The tests will consist of increasing loads in incremental steps. After settling for each step, the total stress and strain in the sample, and measurements from up to three CyTro-X sensor fibers in each rope will be collected.

The ropes in Group A will be suspended in running seawater in flow through seawater tanks to prevent any contact with the tank bottoms. The ropes will be checked to observe any obvious degradation and to assess biofouling growth,

¹ American Bureau of Shipping. Guidance Notes on the application of fiber rope for offshore mooring. Spring, TX 77389.

² DNV. Design, testing and analysis of offshore fibre ropes. DNV-RP-E305. 2021.

including observations of obvious large settlements of specific organisms and changes in the synthetic rope material including color or obvious degradation. The rope segments will remain in running seawater for three to five months.

At the end of the tests, the ropes will be removed and assessed for total biofouling growth and any signs of degradation. Large amounts of external biofouling will be removed, but internal biofouling will be left in place. The ropes will be exposed to further tests to estimate their remaining fatigue life.

CyTroniQ will analyze the relationship between CyTro-X data collected from different points in the rope, which may include critical points at the end connectors. Data from these locations will be compared to the stress/strain data collected from the tensile laboratory.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

A distributed sensor system embedded in mooring lines can reduce system risk, a significant benefit for owners, insurance underwriters, and permitting agencies. This paper has discussed the CyTro-X quasi-distributed FBG sensor system and described a test program that will provide confidence in the technology.

The primary purpose of the system described is to reduce the overall O&M costs of an offshore installation. However, the embedded technology can also provide a pathway towards cost-effective and efficient offshore monitoring for potential environmental effects of marine energy development. The lack of offshore platforms available in potential marine energy sites has hindered baseline assessments and research that can elucidate potential effects of marine energy devices and arrays on marine animals, habitats, and ecosystem processes. Uncertainty and concerns over potential effects of marine energy development have continued to slow deployments and scaling of marine energy devices up to commercial arrays around the world. These effects include potential injury or death for marine animals due to collisions with operational gear, effects of underwater noise emissions from devices, electromagnetic fields generated from export cables, changes in pelagic and benthic habitats due to anchors foundations and mooring lines, and displacement of migratory species from the presence of large numbers of devices. All these effects must be monitored remotely for safety, yet there is a dearth of integrated systems that can collect data, perform preliminary onboard analysis, and transmit results to shore in near real time. The embedded sensor technology described here has the potential to gather input from a wide range of sensors at sea, provide onboard processes through the data acquisition system, and transmit the outcomes to shore. This added knowledge, coupled with ongoing research studies that place the outcomes in context, could help to provide confidence to regulators and stakeholders, opening the way for wider spread permitting and deployment of marine energy devices.

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7. References

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- [2] Chung, J., Lee, M., Kang, S. A Study of 100 t Tensile Load for SMART Mooring Line Monitoring System Considering Polymer Fiber Creep Characteristics. *The Korean Society of Ocean Engineers. Journal of Ocean Engineering and Technology* 35(4), 266-272, August 2021.

Figure 4. MTS 311.41 Tensile Testing Machine with 500kip capacity. Rope specimens will be directly coupled to the load cell on one end and the actuator on the other with a pin and clevis.